

JAPAN IN THE XI-XV CENTURIES. THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF JAPANESE FEUDALISM. THE CONDITION OF THE PEASANTS. URBAN PLANNING. FORMATION OF A SINGLE STATE

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Abstract. Japan is a country with many years of deep history, while maintaining its national traditions and values, it is currently ranked among the top 10 developed countries. His historical paths served as the basis of his current achievements. This article talks about the formation of Japan in the 11th-15th centuries, the ruling circles, and the condition of the peasantry. At the same time, the formation of the feudal society in the Middle Ages, the plight of the peasants, and the activities of the shoguns are described.

Keywords: emperor, shogun feudal, peasant, samurai, Minomoto, Hojyo Tokimasa, Yoko, Shinden-zukuri, sinden, tainoya, Kyoto, "divine wind", "land of the gods", trade, crafts.

Аннотация. Япония — страна с многолетней глубокой историей, сохраняя свои национальные традиции и ценности, в настоящее время входит в десятку самых развитых стран. Ее исторические пути послужили основой ее нынешних достижений. В данной статье говорится о формировании Японии в XI-XV веках, правящих кругах, положении крестьянства. В то же время описывается становление феодального общества в средние века, бедственное положение крестьян, деятельность сёгунов.

Ключевые слова: император, сёгун, феодал, крестьянин, самурай, Миномото, Ходзё Токимаса, Дзёко, Синдэн-дзукури, синден, тайноя, Киото, «божественный ветер», «земля богов», торговля, ремесла.

Since ancient times, tribes and peoples who did not have statehood lived on the territory of Japan. The unification of tribes under the rule of one ruler happened around the 4th century. From this time the medieval history of Japan begins.

Japan is located in the islands east of China and Korea. Because of its geographical location, the country was rarely invaded by foreigners during the Middle Ages, had little contact with other countries, and therefore developed in isolation. The emperor was at the head of Japan. He was considered the son of the sun goddess Amaterasu, so his power was considered sacred. The emperor was called "tenno", which in translation means "heavenly master". All the lands of the empire were considered his property. However, in practice, the emperor rarely interfered in state affairs. Traditionally, he attended only important court ceremonies, and the empire was ruled by family nobles and many officials. Descendants of the first emperors who ruled in the early Middle Ages are still in nominal power in Japan[1]. The formation of a centralized state according to the Chinese model took place during the Asuka period (592–710). This period got its name because the palaces of the Yamato rulers were located in the valley of the Asuka River (not far from the modern cities of Nara and Kyoto). The Asuka period began during the reign of Empress Suiko (592–628), the first woman to ascend the throne in Japanese history. Suiko's nephew Prince Shotoku (574-622) developed the 17-point Code, which formalized the relationship between the ruler and subjects based on traditional values and mainland teachings -

Confucianism and Buddhism. During the Asuka period, China exerted its greatest cultural and political influence on Japanese society. Bureaucracy structure, management institutions, administrative-territorial division, tax, land use distribution system, architecture, written culture, religious-philosophical teachings were adopted. A period of large-scale change began with the "Taika Reforms" (named after the first motto of the reign: *chàìāngì*, literally great changes) in order to transform Yamato into a "civilized" state according to Chinese ideals. . One of the forms of demonstrating the "civilization" of the court was the introduction of individually assigned ranks for abilities. At the same time, the system of hereditary titles (*kabane*) remained in existence, indicating the origin of the kinship associations of the Uji. At the end of the 7th century. Construction began (694–710) on the Fujiwara palace complex north of Asuka, which became Japan's first permanent capital. Japan during the Nara period by the beginning of the 8th century. Strong control was established over the central provinces, the Hayato tribes in Kyushu were pacified, and the Emishi (proto-Ain) tribes were pushed to the northeast. In 702, the country changed its name from Yamato to Nihon (*rínbnò* - Land of the Rising Sun). In 710, the capital was moved from Fujiwara to Heijo (Nara). This was the beginning of a new period in the history of Japan - the Nara period (710-794). The creation of a centralized "law-based" state (*kīnīnīnī*, *ritsuryō kōkka*) was completed. The first legal codes, mythological and chronicle codes, land descriptions, genealogical lists, poetic anthologies were compiled. The laws strengthened the status of the tenno sovereign as Shinto's high priest and head of state, strengthened the structure of the administrative apparatus, established the tax system, and approved the procedure for conducting religious ceremonies. The legitimization of supreme power was based on the Shinto legend of the descent of an uninterrupted and irreplaceable dynasty of sovereigns from the sun goddess Amaterasu. The monk Dokyo's attempt to seize the throne in 769 was the only attempt in Japanese history by a ruling dynasty not represented by the sovereign family. The establishment of the first shogunate, the Minamoto shogunate, determined the process of the formation of a feudal system with developed vassal relations and the social and political dominance of the samurai class. The warriors of the military units were called samurai. Their masters gave them land in exchange for military service. Over the years, some of the Japanese samurai became a separate category, small nobles, like European knights. Warriors who did not have their own land lived on military spoils or on the expense of their masters. This period (1185-1333) was called Kamakura because it was the headquarters of the first shogun. The beginning of the Minamoto shogunate can be traced back to 1192, when Minamoto Yoritomo received the appointment of *sei taishogun* (*kái táishogun* - great commander, conqueror of barbarians) from the sovereign, legitimizing his authority as the head of the military houses. After that, Yoritomo appointed military governors - provincial "protectors" (*kāngī*, *shugo*) and "land chiefs" (*jānjito*, *jito*) in shoen fiefdoms - to maintain order and control local authorities. Direct vassals of the shogun - *gokenin* (*kāngāngān* - man of the house) were assigned to these positions. After the death of Minamoto Yoritomo, the shoguns were removed from direct decision-making and became nominal military rulers. Real power in the bakufu passed into the hands of the shogun's "deputy" - *shikken* (*kānīn* - holder of power). Shogun Minamoto Sanetomo's first *shikken* in 1203 was his grandfather Hojo Tokimasa. Since then, the position has passed through the Hojo family. In 1221, the "monk ruler" Go-Toba (reigned 1183-1198), the capital and military nobles, influential temples and shrines, resenting the power of the *shikken*, rebelled against the House of Hojo, but was defeated. sent to exile (the so-called upheavals of the Jokyu years). The era of "rule from the chapel" was over, all power was in the hands of *Shikken Khojo*. In Kyoto, a headquarters was established for the observer of the

sovereign's court, who intervened in the sovereign's affairs until the selection of the heir to the throne (kāngāngāngāngīshī, Rokuhara tandai) [2]. The imperial power weakened, and soon the real power was transferred to the hands of the most powerful landowner and military commander in the country, the Shogun. Originally, the shogunate was established by one of the local lords, Minamoto, from the end of the 12th century. He defeats his opponents with his samurai army and captures Kyoto, the imperial capital. But Minamoto ruled the country from his castle palace in Kamakura. In this way, dual power will appear in Japan. Shogun - (Japanese for "general") - a title given first by Japanese generals and then by Japanese rulers. The leading role in the leadership of the state was played by families (clans) of tribal nobles with many children. Their representatives occupied the most important positions and became military leaders. In contrast to Chinese practice, positions and positions in Japan are inherited. Thus, individual families of the nobility have maintained their high status for centuries.

In 1274 and 1281, the Mongols conquered China and Korea and invaded Japan twice. Attempts to conquer Japan ended in failure: in 1281, a typhoon, later called the "divine wind" (kinin, kamikaze) by the Japanese, destroyed the Mongol fleet. The main role in the defense of the country was played by the bakufu, whose actions were led by Hojo Tokimune (1251–1284). Gokenin began to serve as a mandatory guard in strategically important areas of the country to protect against the enemy. This led to the strengthening of the military power and independence of the southwestern provinces. A large number of warships were built to defend against the Mongols, and Japanese pirates (wako) and merchant seamen began to use them to sail to China, Korea, and Southeast Asia. Piracy and trade enriched the south of the country. In the second half of the 13th century. Commodity-money relations developed in Japan, involving associations of artisans (za), carriers and merchants (toimaru). Sovereign Go-Daigo (reigned 1318-1339) opposed the power of the bakufu, around him gathered representatives of the military and capital aristocracy, servants of large temples and shrines who were dissatisfied with the political rule of Hojo. In 1333, Ashikaga Takauji (1305-1358), who was sent by the military government to suppress the rebellion, sided with Go-Daigo and became viceroy of the bakufu in Kyoto (kíníííí, Kemmu Shinsei - Restoration of Kemmu, 1333–1336). Taking advantage of the weakening of the Bakufu, Nitta Yoshisada (1301–1338), a representative of the Minamoto faction, captured Kamakura. The last, 16th shikken from Khojo's house committed suicide. In 1336, Ashikaga Takauji captured Kyoto and installed a sovereign from another branch of the dynasty against Go-Daigo's will. Go-Daigo fled to Yoshino, where he founded the "Southern Court". For almost half a century, Japan was ruled by two sovereigns - the "southern court" in Yoshino and the "northern court" in Kyoto; the period of their confrontation went down in history as the period of the "southern and northern dynasties" (jángján, nambokucho; 1336–1392). In 1338, Ashikaga Takauji was officially proclaimed shogun, marking the beginning of a new era - the Ashikaga shogunate (1338–1573) or the Muromachi period (named after the location of the headquarters of the Ashikaga shoguns in the Muromachi region of Kyoto from 1378). In 1392, the two courts were reunited at the initiative of shogun Ashikaga Yoshimitsu (1358–1408) [3].

During the Ashikaga period, all power was in the hands of the shogun, but his direct control extended only to the lands of the capital. As the shugo became stronger in the provinces and the land holdings under their control increased, they became sovereign princes (shugo daimyo). The desire of the latter to expand their possessions led to mutual wars. The "Troubles of Onin" (1467–1477), in which the capital Kyoto was almost completely burned down, marked the beginning of the "age of warring provinces" (sangou jidai, 1467–1568). The most important political, economic and cultural centers of Japan were located on three large islands: Honshu,

Kyushu and Shikoku. Smaller islands, as well as the large northern island of Hokkaido, served as a zone of military expansion and gradual expansion of state borders for many centuries. Japan's closest neighbors, China and Korea, suffered from regular attacks by Japanese pirates on merchant ships and coastal areas.

The most effective means of political struggle in traditional Japan was establishing family ties with the imperial house and holding positions that allowed the ruler to dictate his will. Representatives of the Fujiwara clan were more successful in this regard than others, for a long time they supplied brides to the emperors, and from 866 they had a monopoly on appointing sessho regents and a little later (from 887) kampaku chancellors. In 866, Fujiwara Yoshifusa became the first non-imperial regent in Japanese history. Regents acted on behalf of child emperors who lacked political will, while chancellors represented adult rulers. They not only controlled current affairs, but also determined the order of succession to the throne, forcing the most active rulers to abdicate in favor of younger heirs, as a rule, who had family ties to the Fujiwaras. By 967, the regents and chancellors would gain the most power. Over time, they lose their influence, but the positions are not canceled. Japanese political culture is characterized by the nominal preservation of old institutions of power and the creation of new ones that duplicate their functions [4].

Growth of urban civilization in 10-12 centuries. led to significant development of secular architecture. A new type of residence takes on the characteristics of a so-called ensemble. Sinden-zukuri style, which continues national architectural traditions, is combined with continental architectural experience. A wide single-hall portico of unpainted wood (sinden) raised on columns, connected by galleries (tainoya) on both sides, connected the main building with the rest of the ensemble. The facade of Shinden opens onto a sandy area, ending in a large landscaped garden with islands, bridges, rocks and works of art, a lake (the Imperial Palace in Kyoto, restored in 1789 on a 9th-century model) in the southern part. Along with sculpture, ornaments and wall paintings took an increasingly important place in the decoration of the temple interior [6].

With the transition of power in the 12th-14th centuries. to the military-feudal class (called the Kamakura period after the shogunate capital Minamoto) Japanese art becomes the property of wider circles; there is a desire for simplicity, a combination of religious and secular principles. Monasteries of the Zen sect, modeled after China, dominated by a building of columns, beams, and light sections (the main building of Engakuji Monastery in Kamakura, 1285), are characteristic of this period. The style of residential architecture is also becoming strictly simple and reasonable. Kamakura period sculpture focused on the authenticity and monumental importance of images. The art of sculptural portraiture developed rapidly (workshops of sculptors Kokey and Unkey); Legendary propagators of Buddhism (Mutuaku, Seshin, Kuya, etc.), Shinto saints (Hachimon, etc.), as well as military leaders are widely depicted and canonized. In the 12th-14th centuries, portraits of warriors and monks were also common in paintings. There was a growing desire to describe in detail in the pictorial ekimono sheets. In the decorative and applied arts, the decoration of swords and daggers, including tsu-bu, saddles, harnesses, etc., has risen to a high level. [7].

At the beginning of the Middle Ages in Japan, crafts and trade were poorly developed and almost inseparable: whoever produced goods sold them. But over time the situation changed. It was mainly helped by migrant craftsmen from China and Korea. By the XIII-XIV centuries. Japanese craftsmen achieved high skill in metal processing and fabric making. As crafts developed, the population of cities increased.

Peasants made up the majority of the population of medieval Japan. Peasants were engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry. The main agricultural crop was rice. Wheat, soybeans, and various vegetables were also grown. Fishing played an important economic role in coastal regions. Peasants lived in close-knit communities where family and kinship ties were very important. Farmers paid taxes to the state based on the amount of cultivated land. [5]

Socially, medieval Japan was highly hierarchical, with clearly defined classes, with samurai holding privileged positions, and peasants and merchants occupying lower statuses. This class division affected the political and cultural life of the country. In short, the medieval history of Japan is of great importance in the formation of modern strategic Japan. It was the feudal period in which the main social structures and cultural traditions were formed, which had a long-term impact on the country's development and identity. Created unique values and traditions that continue to influence Japanese society in the modern world.

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